

Thermodynamic Study of Mixed Complexes of Cd(II) with Ethylenediamine and Adipate at Dropping Mercury Electrode

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Polarographic measurements have been used to determine the overall formation constants of simple and mixed complexes of Cd(II) with adipate and ethylenediamine. The Schaap and McMasters' treatment reveals the presence of three mixed complexes in aqueous medium. The overall formation constants (log values) β_{11} , β_{12} and β_{21} for complexes $[\text{Cd}(\text{en})(\text{Adip})]$; $[\text{Cd}(\text{en})(\text{Adip})_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{en})_2(\text{Adip})]$ are 10.21, 10.27, 11.00 respectively at 298°K. Thermodynamic parameters of the mixed complexes have been calculated and reported here. Tendencies of a ligand to add and replace another ligand from a simple or mixed complex is discussed.

LITERATURE reveals that Cd(II) forms 1 : 3 highest complexes with ethylenediamine and adipate separately. The DeFord and Hume's¹ method for simple complexes was extended to study the formation constants of mixed complexes by Schaap and McMasters². The mixed complexes of various metal ions with organic ligands particularly dicarboxylic acids have been studied in our laboratory³⁻⁴ and also by others⁵⁻⁷ using polarographic measurements. Here we wish to report mixed complexes of Cd(II) with ethylenediamine and adipate.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade purity. The solution of $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, KNO_3 and sodium adipate and ethylenediamine were prepared in double distilled water. KNO_3 was used as supporting electrolyte to maintain the ionic strength constant at 2.0 M. All solutions contained 5×10^{-4} M Cd^{2+} . For mixed complex formation the fixed concentration of adipate were 0.10 M and 0.25 M.

The temperatures were maintained constant at $298 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{K}$ and $308 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{K}$ using U₉ Ger Mer 8354 type thermostat. The capillary of d.m.e. had the following characteristics $m=2.14$ mg/sec; $t=4.6$ sec at the height 65 cm of the mercury head.

Results and Discussion

The reduction of Cd^{2+} in medium of adipate and ethylenediamine was found reversible and diffusion controlled as revealed from straight line plots of i_d vs $h_{\text{drt}}^{3/2}$ of mercury column passing through the origin. The slopes of the straight line plots of $\log i/i_{\text{d}}-i$ vs $E_{\text{d.e.}}$ were 30 to 32 mV.

Overall formation constants (log values) of simple complexes were determined by DeFord and Hume's method using the polarographic measurements. The results are summarised below :

Complex Species	Overall formation constants at	
	298°K	308°K
$[\text{Cd}(\text{Adip})]$; $\log \beta_{01}$	1.25	1.00
$[\text{Cd}(\text{Adip})_2]^{2-}$; $\log \beta_{02}$	1.56	1.30
$[\text{Cd}(\text{Adip})_3]^{4-}$; $\log \beta_{03}$	2.74	2.60
$[\text{Cd}(\text{en})]^{2+}$; $\log \beta_{10}$	9.62	8.30
$[\text{Cd}(\text{en})_2]^{2+}$; $\log \beta_{20}$	10.00	9.00
$[\text{Cd}(\text{en})_3]^{2+}$; $\log \beta_{30}$	12.00	11.48

The two fixed concentrations of adipate are 0.10 M and 0.25 M.

The overall formation constants (log values) of mixed complexes at 298°K are shown in scheme and at 308°K are 8.93; 9.12; and 10.56. These values were determined using polarographic measurements which are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC MEASUREMENTS OF Cd(ADIPATE)(ETHYLENEDIAMINE MIXED SYSTEM

	C_x	$-E_{1/2}$ in V vs SCE		i_d in div at	
		298°K	308°K	298°K	308°K
Set A	0.00	0.6060	0.6000	59	65
	0.16	0.9245	0.8890	45	52
Set B	0.00	0.6060	0.6000	59	65
	0.16	0.9040	0.8910	45	48

C_x = concentration of Ethylenediamine in mole litre⁻¹.

In sets B and A the concentration of adipate are kept fixed at 0.10 M and 0.25 M respectively.

Thermodynamic parameters of mixed complexes are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Complex Species	Thermodynamic Parameters		
	ΔH° K cal mole ⁻¹	ΔF° K cal mole ⁻¹	ΔS° cal deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹
[Cd(en)(Adip)]	-54.78	-14.15	-134.90
[Cd(en)(Adip) ₂] ²⁻	-49.41	-14.24	-118.50
[Cd(en) ₂ (Adip)]	-19.11	-15.25	-12.80

Cd(II) is hexa coordinated, three mixed complexes thus existing in solution are schematically shown.

In the scheme the numerical values are log K values, where K is the equilibrium constant of the

step-indicated in the summary. X²⁻ and Y stand for adipate and ethylenediamine respectively.

From the scheme it is seen that [Cd(X)] can add to Y more easily than X²⁻. The two unsaturated complexes [Cd(X)] and [Cd(Y)]²⁺ can add Y and X respectively forming Cd(X)(Y). The relative tendencies of addition shows that Y is a much stronger ligand than X²⁻, [Cd(Y)]²⁺ can add X²⁻ as well as Y but here the addition of X²⁻ is rather easier than Y; this clearly shows that the mixed complex formation is favoured over simple. Several other reactions show similar tendency of mixed complex formation. [Cd(Y)₃]²⁺, however, does not have tendency to form mixed complex.

In the same way the tendency of ligand molecules to add to a complex and to be substituted in place of another ligand may be compared.

The stability of three mixed complexes as seen from the overall formation constant values follows the order :

References

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